

SMS Spam Detection Using Machine Learning

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Abstract. These days usage of mobiles is increasing rapidly. SMS (Short message service) is available on any type of mobile phone to contact and share information. We are using this SMS for OTPs, conversations, etc.... So, the SMS importance and usage increased rapidly with this Spam messages also increased day by day regarding business, credit cards, loans, lottery tickets, etc... In this paper, we collect the dataset from Kaggle.com and use different types of ML techniques for messages detection. We achieved the highest accuracy with the Random Forest classifier of 97.90% for SMS SPAM Detection.

Keywords: SMS Spam, Machine learning, dataset, Random Forest.

1. Introduction

Short Message Service (SMS) is a way for transmitting text messages between devices. The term "spam" is used to describe messages or information that is unwanted or useless. Therefore, Every unsolicited text delivered to a smart phone is considered SMS spam. Currently, spam has become a big problem in messaging apps. Even yet, many continue to fall for spam communications, revealing their passwords, account information, and private documents.

Spammers typically issue these spam messages to promote their services or businesses. These spam communications might occasionally cause users to lose money. With the use of machine learning, computers can infer future data from historical data. Datasets for training and testing methods for SMS spam detection are few and tiny. Moreover, text messages are shorter than emails and contain statistically differentiable information, which reduces the need for a variety of methods to identify spam SMS. Email spam filtering techniques for SMS fail due to the strong effect of informal languages in text messages, such as regional vocabulary, idioms, phrases, and acronyms.

2. Literature Survey

In this section, we are going to compare distinct types of ML techniques used by previous researchers on spam detection. Sridevi [1] et. al applied ML techniques and attained an efficiency of 97.5%. Pavas Navaney [2] et. al used Maximum entropy classifier and attained an efficiency of 97.4% by SVM algorithm. Sahar, Bosaeed [3] et. al used ML techniques like the Support vector machine algorithm, Naive Bayes, and naïve Bayes multinomial classifier and attained an efficiency of 98.8% by SVM algorithm. Mehul Gupta [4] et. al applied ML techniques and attained an accuracy of 94.2%.

3. Methodology

Dataset Description

We looked through several websites for the dataset before selecting the one from the Kaggle website, which has a total of 5572 entries with two columns each. Whether the communication is "spam" or "ham" is indicated in the first column. The real message is in the second column. If the first column in this case contains spam, the

message is considered junk mail, and ham denotes a helpful message.

Fig 1. Dataset model

	label	sms
0	ham	Go until jurong point, crazy.. Available only ...
1	ham	Ok lar... Joking wif u oni...
2	spam	Free entry in 2 a wkly comp to win FA Cup fina...
3	ham	U dun say so early hor... U c already then say...
4	ham	Nah I don't think he goes to usf, he lives aro...

DATA PREPROCESSING

We perform the data pre-processing, on the data set to reduce the features. We start with on version, pre-processing, removing stop words and steaming, vectorization / Feature extraction, and splitting of datasets accordance with algorithm's requirement. Using various models training and testing will be done.

Fig 2. After removing stop words and steaming the dataset

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0      Go until jurong point, crazy.. Available only ...
1      Ok lar... Joking wif u oni...
2      Free entry in 2 a wkly comp to win FA Cup fina...
3      U dun say so early hor... U c already then say...
4      Nah I don't think he goes to usf, he lives aro...
...
5567   This is the 2nd time we have tried 2 contact u...
5568   Will i_b going to esplanade fr home?
5569   Pity, * was in mood for that. So...any other s...
5570   The guy did some bitching but I acted like i'd...
5571   Rofl. Its true to its name
Name: sms, Length: 5572, dtype: object

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Evaluation Matrix:

The terms precision, recall, and accuracy are used to compare how well classifiers work.

TP= True Positives

FP= False Positives

TN=True Negatives

FN=False Negatives

$P = TP / (TP + FP)$

$R = TP / (TP + FN)$

$Acc = ((TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN))$.

$F1 = 2 * ((precision * recall) / (precision + recall))$

Different Classifiers

Logistic regression:

An example of a supervised learning algorithm is this one. This is what we utilise to forecast the categorical dependent variable. Possible outcomes include True, False, yes, no, 0 or 1, Pass, or Fail. This algorithm gives us a 95.33% accuracy rate.

Fig 3. Classification report

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.95	0.99	0.97	1453
1	0.94	0.68	0.79	219
accuracy			0.95	1672
macro avg	0.95	0.84	0.88	1672
weighted avg	0.95	0.95	0.95	1672

Fig 4. Confusion Matrix

Confusion matrix, without normalization
[[1444 9]
[69 150]]

Naïve Bayes:

This algorithm is based on a probability model which helps to find the probability of an event. Here we use in-text classifiers that include high-dimensional datasets. By this algorithm, we get an accuracy of 97.72%.

Fig 5. Classification report

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.98	0.99	0.99	1453
1	0.94	0.88	0.91	219
accuracy			0.98	1672
macro avg	0.96	0.94	0.95	1672
weighted avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	1672

Fig 6. Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization
[[1441 12]
[26 193]]

KNN:

A non-parametric, supervised machine learning classifier is K-Nearest Neighbour (K-NN). In this approach, we take into account the differences in resemblance between new and existing data and classify the new data into K-NN category that most closely resembles the existing data. This algorithm gives us a 93.95% accuracy rate.

Fig 7. Confusion Matrix

Confusion matrix, without normalization
 $\begin{bmatrix} 1451 & 2 \\ 99 & 120 \end{bmatrix}$

Support vector Machine:

Support Vector Machine (SVM), is widely used ML method is utilised for both classifying and regression issues. With this model, we have a 97.84% accuracy rate.

Fig 8. Classification report

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.98	1.00	0.99	1453
1	0.96	0.87	0.91	219
accuracy			0.98	1672
macro avg	0.97	0.93	0.95	1672
weighted avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	1672

Fig 9. Confusion matrix

Confusion matrix, without normalization
 $\begin{bmatrix} 1446 & 7 \\ 29 & 190 \end{bmatrix}$

Decision tree classification:

Both classification and regression issues can be resolved using a decision tree, however classification issues are the most frequently addressed. This approach uses a tree-structured classifier, in which nodes stand in for dataset features, branches for rules, and leaf nodes for results. This method gave us a 95.81% accuracy rate.

Fig 10. Classification report

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.98	0.98	0.98	1453
1	0.84	0.84	0.84	219
accuracy			0.96	1672
macro avg	0.91	0.91	0.91	1672
weighted avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	1672

Fig 11. Confusion Matrix

Confusion matrix, without normalization
[[1418 35]
[35 184]]

Random forest:

Random Forest is a classification method that utilize decision tree on discrete dataset subsets and average the outcomes to improve the dataset's projected accuracy. We find that this algorithm's 97.90% accuracy is the best for this project.

Fig 12: Classification report

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.98	1.00	0.99	1453
1	1.00	0.84	0.91	219
accuracy			0.98	1672
macro avg	0.99	0.92	0.95	1672
weighted avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	1672

Fig 13: Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization
[[1453 0]
[35 184]]

4. Experimental Result:

After applying all ML classifiers, we applied Random Forest for the same dataset and achieved an accuracy of 97.90%. Fig 14 represents the comparison between Accuracy, Prediction, Recall, and F-measure from all the classification techniques used.

Fig 14. Comparison between Classifiers

	Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-measure
0	LogisticRegression	0.953349	0.943396	0.684932	0.793651
1	MNB	0.977273	0.941463	0.881279	0.910377
2	KNN	0.939593	0.983607	0.547945	0.703812
3	SVM	0.978469	0.964467	0.867580	0.913462
4	Decision Tree	0.958134	0.840183	0.840183	0.840183
5	Random Forest	0.979067	1.000000	0.840183	0.913151

Fig 15: Graph representation of distribution by Classifiers

5. Conclusion

On the training data set, we have applied various ML classifiers, including support vector machines, decision trees, KNN, logistic regression, naive Bayes, and random forests. By comparing the accuracy of different classifiers, we observed the random forest classifier had the highest accuracy, at 97.90%. We will be able to apply new ways to update diverse datasets in the future.

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